

General Relativity Reinterpreted as a Variable-Speed-of-Light Theory.

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Abstract

Aims. We demonstrate that general relativity can be interpreted as a variable speed of light theory instead of spacetime curvature model and this interpretation is falsifiable.

Methods. We define a transformation that modifies the speed of light in the four spacetime directions to ensure that the energy $E = mc^2$ remains invariant across all proper reference frames. For example, if \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{C}' are two proper reference frames at rest relative to each other, the transformation for the x -direction is given by $dx' = dx/\sqrt{a_1}$, $dt' = dt \sqrt{a_1}$, $dy' = dy$ and $dz' = dz$, where a_1 is a parameter representing the variation of the speed of light caused by the mass distribution. Radiation emitted from \mathcal{C}' at a speed c and a frequency ν_0 is observed from \mathcal{C} at a speed $a_1 c$ and a frequency $\sqrt{a_1} \nu_0$.

Results. This approach yields results equivalent to those of the spacetime curvature model in most of cases, such as the Schwarzschild metric or the motion of a massive particle, among others. However, significant differences arise: the gravitational force results from variations in the parameters a_i (where i denotes the spacetime direction), the light travel time along the length of a material object depends on the parameters a_i , the apparent expansion of the universe is attributed to an increase in the parameter a_0 with respect to time.

Keywords: General relativity, Special relativity, Variable speed of light, Cosmological constant, Black energy.

1 Introduction

General and special relativity are the only two theories that modify the measurement of time and spatial intervals. Paradoxically, they are based on fundamentally different principles: the invariance of the speed of light for the former and spacetime curvature for the latter.

We demonstrate that a common principle can be defined for both special and general relativity, provided the invariant speed of light postulate is modified: the speed of light remains invariant within the observer's reference frame, but relative to this reference frame, it can vary across time and space. Consequently, in general relativity, the speed of light assumes a role analogous to that of

mass in special relativity.

The energy E of a massive particle depends on its mass m and on the speed of light c as described by Einstein's formula: $E = mc^2$. If either of these parameters changes when observed from another reference frame, the energy of the particle is altered. To maintain the invariance of these parameters in the new reference frame, a coordinate transformation must be applied.

Special relativity addresses the relative change in mass, and the Lorentz transformation ensures the invariance of energy in every inertial reference frame where the particle is at rest.

We demonstrate that general relativity addresses the relative change in the speed of light. We define a transformation, denoted by S , that maintains the invariance of energy in every reference frame where the particle is at rest, despite variations in the relative speed of light. The force required to move between reference frames is the gravitational force. Direct measurement of the relative change in the speed of light is impossible because all measurements are performed in a proper reference frame where the speed of light is invariant; however, indirect measurements, such as changes in light travel time, number of wavelengths, or frequency, are feasible

This approach remains compatible with Einstein's

equation of general relativity:

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}R + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4}T_{\mu\nu} \quad (1)$$

The S transformation can generate all metric solutions to this equation. However, the proposed interpretation is fundamentally different: space-time is flat, but variations in the speed of light modify the measurement of time and spatial intervals, creating the appearance of curvature.

After justifying and defining the coordinate transformation for the relative change in the speed of light, we present results of this approach in three areas: distance measurement, gravity, and the apparent expansion of the universe.

2 Relative variation in speed of light

The principle of the invariant speed of light in empty space was postulated by A. Einstein in 1905 [1]. In 1911 A. Einstein assumed [2], "*nur in erster Näherung gültig*": *valid only to a first approximation. If c_0 represents the speed of light at the origin of the coordinates, the speed of light c at a location with the gravitation potential Φ is given by the following relation:*

$$c = c_0 (1 + \Phi/c^2) \quad (2)$$

Subsequently, Einstein abandoned the concept of a variable speed of light in favor of general relativity.

In [3] J. Magueijo reviews various varying speed of light theories in "*the arenas of cosmology, quantum gravity and experiment/observation*". He notes that, "*even after the proposal of special relativity in 1905 many varying speed of light theories were considered, most notably by Einstein himself in 1911*".

Although none of these theories have achieved scientific consensus, they demonstrate that the principle of an invariant speed of light continues to be questioned.

2.1 Common principle between special and general relativity

Invariant speed of light in the proper reference frame.

The second and the meter are defined by the International Bureau of Weights and Measures (BIPM) [4] as follows:

"*The second is equal to the duration of 9 192 631 770 periods of the radiation corresponding to the transition between the two hyperfine levels of the unperturbed ground state of the ^{133}Cs atom.*". Let $\nu_0 = 9\,192\,631\,770\text{ Hz}$ denote this frequency.

"*The meter is the length of the path travelled by*

light (speed of light $c = 299\,792\,458\text{ m/s}$) in vacuum during a time interval with duration of $1/299\,792\,458$ of a second"

Measuring a time or space interval involves counting, in the reference frame where the radiation is emitted, the number of time periods T_0 or wavelengths λ_0 of this radiation:

$$\begin{aligned} T_0 &= 1/\nu_0 = 1.087310^{-10}\text{ s} \\ \lambda_0 &= cT_0 = 0.032612256\text{ m} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The speed of light can be defined as the ratio of a length period (wavelength) to a time period; thus, the speed of light is always one in any proper reference frame.

If this radiation is emitted from the reference frame \mathcal{C}' , its frequency and/or speed, as observed from another reference frame \mathcal{C} , may differ, leading to modified measurements of time and spatial intervals. If the speed of light, as observed from \mathcal{C} , is invariant, it is special relativity; otherwise, it is general relativity.

This principle of invariant speed of light in every proper reference frame, despite its relative variation between reference frames, enables the definition of a coordinate transformation to move between reference frames.

Energy perspective.

The rest energy $E = mc^2$ of a massive particle, where m is its rest mass and c is the speed of light, is invariant in all proper reference frames, as are

m and c . However, when observed from another reference frame, these quantities may vary. The transformation of the time and spatial interval measurements ensures these three parameters (E , m and c) remain invariant in every proper reference frame.

Relative mass variation.

Special relativity addresses the relative variation of mass while the speed of light remains constant. More precisely, when a particle moves from one inertial proper reference frame \mathcal{C}' to another \mathcal{C} moving at a velocity v relative to \mathcal{C}' , the following applies:

- A force \mathbf{F} must be applied to the particle to accelerate it to velocity v .
- For an observer in \mathcal{C}' , the mass and energy of the particle appear to increase by a factor $\gamma = 1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$;
- The coordinates in \mathcal{C} are obtained via the Lorentz transformation, which modifies the measurements of time and spatial intervals.
- Through the coordinate transformation, the rest mass and energy of the particle, as observed in \mathcal{C} , remain unchanged.

Relative variation in the speed of light.

What would happen if the energy of the particle were modified not by a relative variation in mass but by a relative variation in the speed of light? This implies moving to another reference frame \mathcal{C} , at rest relative to \mathcal{C}' , but where the speed of light

differs from that in \mathcal{C}' . Although the speed of light and the energy of the particle, as observed in \mathcal{C} , differ from those in \mathcal{C}' , they remain unchanged in the proper reference frame \mathcal{C} . This necessitates a coordinate transformation. The force required to change the energy of the particle, as observed from \mathcal{C}' , is the gravitational force.

Thus, both special and general relativity, through coordinate transformations, ensure the invariance of the rest mass, the energy of a massive particle, and the speed of light when moving from one proper reference frame to another.

2.2 Coordinate transformation in one dimension

Relativity of the speed of light.

Let \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{C}' be two proper reference frames with zero relative velocity. The general case of moving frames will be addressed by eliminating the relative velocity through a Lorentz transformation. Let \mathbf{e}_i and \mathbf{e}'_i ($i = 0, 1, 2, 3$) be two orthonormal bases of \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{C}' , respectively. The vectors \mathbf{e}_i and \mathbf{e}'_i are collinear and oriented in the same direction. The coordinates x^i and x'^i denote the coordinates of an event in \mathbf{e}_i and \mathbf{e}'_i , respectively.

The speed of radiation emitted from \mathcal{C}' along the direction x^i is c in the basis \mathbf{e}'_i but is $a_i c$ in the basis \mathbf{e}_i (as observed from \mathcal{C}). Conversely, the speed of radiation emitted from \mathcal{C} along the direction x^i is c in the basis \mathbf{e}_i but is c/a_i in the basis

\mathbf{e}'_i (as observed from \mathcal{C}').

Transformation.

We assume that the speed of radiation emitted from \mathcal{C}' is c in the basis \mathbf{e}'_i and, as observed from \mathcal{C} is, $a_1 c$ in the direction \mathbf{e}_1 and c in the other directions. Let us define the matrix that transforms the intervals dx^i into dx'^i and vice versa.

Intervals dx^2 and dx^3 .

Since the speed of light is invariant in the directions \mathbf{e}_2 and \mathbf{e}_3 and the relative velocity between the two reference frames is zero, the following holds:

$$dx^2 = dx'^2, \quad dx^3 = dx'^3. \quad (4)$$

Intervals dx^0 et dx^1 .

We seek a linear relation between primed and unprimed intervals:

$$\begin{aligned} dx^0 &= \alpha dx'^0 + \gamma dx'^1, \\ dx^1 &= \delta dx'^0 + \beta dx'^1. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Since the relative velocity between the two referential frames is zero, if $dx^1 = 0$, then $dx'^1 = 0$, for any value of dx'^0 . Consequently, $\delta = 0$. Similarly, if $dx^0 = 0$, then $dx'^0 = 0$, for any value of dx'^1 . Thus, $\gamma = 0$.

Given the condition that if $\frac{dx'^1}{dx'^0} = c$, then $\frac{dx^1}{dx^0} = a_1 c$, we can determine α and β such that:

$$dx^0 = \alpha dx'^0, \quad dx^1 = \beta dx'^1, \quad (6)$$

Fig. 1 Position versus time of radiation emitted from \mathcal{C}' as observed in \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{C}'

with

$$\frac{\beta}{\alpha} = a_1. \quad (7)$$

To illustrate the relationship between the primed and unprimed intervals, we have plotted in Figure 1 the position of radiation emitted from \mathcal{C}' as a function of time in the two bases \mathbf{e}'_i and \mathbf{e}_i . The slope of the lines are c and $a_1 c$ in the bases \mathbf{e}'_i and \mathbf{e}_i , respectively.

The light travels the spatial interval dx'^1 (in the basis \mathbf{e}'_i) in the time interval dx'^0 (in the basis \mathbf{e}'_i):

$$dx'^1 = a_1 c dx'^0. \quad (8)$$

Likewise, the light travels the space interval dx^1 (in the basis \mathbf{e}_i) in a time interval dx^0 (in the basis \mathbf{e}_i):

$$dx^1 = a_1 c dx^0. \quad (9)$$

From eqs. (8) and (9), we obtain:

$$dx'^0 dx'^1 = dx^0 dx^1. \quad (10)$$

From eqs. (6) and (10), we obtain:

$$\alpha \beta = 1. \quad (11)$$

We choose a positive α such that dx'^i and dx^i have the same sign. Using eq. (7), α and β are given by:

$$\alpha = 1/\sqrt{a_1}, \quad \beta = \sqrt{a_1}. \quad (12)$$

The transformation is thus defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} dx^0 &= dx'^0 / \sqrt{a_1}, \\ dx^1 &= \sqrt{a_1} dx'^1, \\ dx^2 &= dx'^2, \\ dx^3 &= dx'^3. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

We can evaluate the effect of this transformation on a monochromatic electromagnetic plane wave emitted from \mathcal{C}' with frequency ν_0 and propagation speed c along the x' -direction. Its equation in the basis \mathbf{e}'_i is expressed as:

$$\mathcal{A}'(x', t') = \mathcal{A}'_0 \cos \left(2\pi \nu_0 \left(t' - \frac{x'}{c} \right) \right). \quad (14)$$

The equation can be expressed in the basis \mathbf{e}_i using the transformation $x' = x/\sqrt{a_1}$ and $t' = \sqrt{a_1} t$, ($a_1 > 0$):

$$\mathcal{A}'(x, t) = \mathcal{A}'_0 \cos \left(2\pi \sqrt{a_1} \nu_0 \left(t - \frac{x}{a_1 c} \right) \right). \quad (15)$$

This results in the equation of a monochromatic electromagnetic plane wave with a frequency of $\sqrt{a_1} \nu_0$ and a propagation speed of $a_1 c$. To increase the speed of light by a factor a_1 , the wavelength is multiplied by $\sqrt{a_1}$ and the time period is multiplied by $1/\sqrt{a_1}$.

2.3 Coordinate transformation in four-dimensional spacetime

The transformations for the two remaining spatial directions \mathbf{e}_2 and \mathbf{e}_3 can be derived directly. We adopt speed ratios of a_2 and a_3 , respectively.

If the relative speed of light varies over time by a factor a_0 , the three spatial directions are modified identically:

$$\begin{aligned} dx^0 &= dx'^0 / \sqrt{a_0}, \\ dx^1 &= \sqrt{a_0} dx'^1, \\ dx^2 &= \sqrt{a_0} dx'^2, \\ dx^3 &= \sqrt{a_0} dx'^3. \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Thus, four elementary transformations have been defined to transform the intervals dx^μ into dx'^μ :

$$\frac{\partial x^\mu}{\partial x'^\nu} = S_0^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{a_0}} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \sqrt{a_0} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \sqrt{a_0} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \sqrt{a_0} \end{pmatrix},$$

$$\frac{\partial x^\mu}{\partial x'^\nu} = S_1^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{a_1}} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \sqrt{a_1} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$\frac{\partial x^\mu}{\partial x'^\nu} = S_2^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{a_2}} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \sqrt{a_2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$\frac{\partial x^\mu}{\partial x'^\nu} = S_3^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{a_3}} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \sqrt{a_3} \end{pmatrix}.$$

The general transformation S^{-1} is the composition of these four transformations:

$$S = \frac{\partial x'^\mu}{\partial x^\nu} = S_0 S_1 S_2 S_3 = \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{a_0 a_1 a_2 a_3} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1/\sqrt{a_0 a_1} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1/\sqrt{a_0 a_2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/\sqrt{a_0 a_3} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (17)$$

The matrix S matrix transforms the intervals dx^μ into dx'^μ when the relative speed of light varies across the four directions between two reference frames zero relative velocity.

2.4 Solutions to Einstein's equation

All metrics $g_{\mu\nu}$ that satisfy Einstein's eq. (1) can be obtained through a S transformation. As $g_{\mu\nu}$ is a real symmetric matrix, it can be diagonalized.

In this basis, the metric can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} ds^2 &= g_{\mu\nu} dx^\mu dx^\nu \\ &= -b_0^2 (dx^0)^2 + b_1^2 (dx^1)^2 \\ &\quad + b_2^2 (dx^2)^2 + b_3^2 (dx^3)^2. \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

A metric can also be expressed to account for the relative change in the speed of light across the four directions of spacetime:

$$\begin{aligned} ds^2 &= (S.ds)^t \cdot \eta \cdot S.ds \\ &= -a_0 a_1 a_2 a_3 (dx^0)^2 \\ &\quad + \frac{(dx^1)^2}{a_0 a_1} + \frac{(dx^2)^2}{a_0 a_2} + \frac{(dx^3)^2}{a_0 a_3}, \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

where η is given by:

$$\eta = \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

The coefficients of the metrics in eqs. (18) and (19) must be identical. If all b_μ^2 are positive, then:

$$\begin{aligned} b_0^2 &= a_0 a_1 a_2 a_3 & a_0 &= 1/\sqrt{b_0^2 b_1^2 b_2^2 b_3^2} \\ b_1^2 &= 1/(a_0 a_1) & a_1 &= \sqrt{b_0^2 b_2^2 b_3^2 / b_1^2} \\ b_2^2 &= 1/(a_0 a_2) & a_2 &= \sqrt{b_0^2 b_1^2 b_3^2 / b_2^2} \\ b_3^2 &= 1/(a_0 a_3) & a_3 &= \sqrt{b_0^2 b_1^2 b_2^2 / b_3^2}. \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

According to Sylvester's law of inertia, the number of positive and negative eigenvalues remains

invariant under a change of basis. Thus, the metric (18) must have consistently one negative and three positive coefficients.

Eq. (20) provides the solution for a negative time coefficient. If the negative coefficient corresponds to x^1 instead of x^0 , then a_1 is given by $-\sqrt{b_0^2 b_2^2 b_3^2 / b_1^2}$, with the other coefficients remaining unchanged. This pattern applies analogously for other cases. Consequently, every metric that satisfies Einstein's equation can be obtained through the composition of the four elementary S_μ transformations.

2.5 The gravitational forces resulting from relative variations in the speed of light

Relative variations in the speed of light across the three spatial dimensions can generate a force.

Notation: \mathbf{Q} is a four-vector, with components Q^{x^i} and Q'^{x^i} defined in the bases \mathbf{e}_i and \mathbf{e}'_i , respectively.

The general metric obtained via the S transformation is given by eq. (19). Setting $a_0 = 1$, the metric is expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} ds^2 &= g_{tt} c^2 dt^2 + g_{xx} dx^2 + g_{yy} dy^2 + g_{zz} dz^2 \\ &= -a_1 a_2 a_3 c^2 dt^2 + \frac{dx^2}{a_1} + \frac{dy^2}{a_2} + \frac{dz^2}{a_3}, \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

where $g_{tt} = -a_1 a_2 a_3$, $g_{xx} = \frac{1}{a_1}$, $g_{yy} = \frac{1}{a_2}$, and $g_{zz} = \frac{1}{a_3}$.

The four-acceleration of a particle is defined as the covariant derivative of its four-velocity with respect to the proper time. For a particle at rest, the four-acceleration is zero:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= \frac{DU^i}{d\tau} \\ &= \frac{dU^i}{d\tau} + \Gamma_{\mu\nu}^i U^\mu U^\nu \\ &= \frac{d^2 x^i}{d\tau^2} + \Gamma_{\mu\nu}^i U^\mu U^\nu, \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

where U^i is the four-velocity, $\Gamma_{\mu\nu}^i$ are the Christoffel symbols, and τ is the proper time. The term $m \frac{d^2 x^i}{d\tau^2}$ represents the gravitational force, denoted by F_g^i .

For a particle at rest, the spatial components of the four-velocity are zero: $U_x = U_y = U_z = 0$. Given the condition $\mathbf{U} \cdot \mathbf{U} = -c^2$, the time component in \mathcal{C}' is $U^{t'} = c$ and in \mathcal{C} , it is $U^t = c/\sqrt{-g_{tt}}$. Simplifying (22), the gravitational force:

$$F_g^i = -\frac{mc^2}{g_{tt}} \Gamma_{tt}^i. \quad (23)$$

The Christoffel symbols are given by:

$$\Gamma_{\mu\nu}^i = \frac{1}{2} g^{i\alpha} (\partial_\mu g_{\nu\alpha} + \partial_\nu g_{\mu\alpha} - \partial_\alpha g_{\mu\nu}). \quad (24)$$

To compute Γ_{tt}^i , set $\mu = \nu = t$. Given the diagonal metric from eq. (21), with $g_{tt} = -a_1 a_2 a_3$, $g^{xx} = a_1$, $g^{yy} = a_2$, $g^{zz} = a_3$, and corresponding

inverse metric components $g^{tt} = -\frac{1}{a_1 a_2 a_3}$, $g^{xx} = a_1$, $g^{yy} = a_2$, $g^{zz} = a_3$, we assume the coefficients a_i depend only on their respective spatial coordinates, i.e., $\frac{da_i}{dx^j} = 0$ for $i \neq j$. Simplifying eq. (24), Γ_{tt}^i components are:

$$\begin{aligned}\Gamma_{tt}^t &= 0, \\ \Gamma_{tt}^x &= -\frac{1}{2}g^{xx}\partial_x g_{tt} = \frac{1}{2}a_1 a_2 a_3 \frac{da_1}{dx}, \\ \Gamma_{tt}^y &= -\frac{1}{2}g^{yy}\partial_y g_{tt} = \frac{1}{2}a_1 a_2 a_3 \frac{da_2}{dy}, \\ \Gamma_{tt}^z &= -\frac{1}{2}g^{zz}\partial_z g_{tt} = \frac{1}{2}a_1 a_2 a_3 \frac{da_3}{dz}.\end{aligned}\quad (25)$$

Using equation (23), and substituting $g_{tt} = -a_1 a_2 a_3$, the gravitational force components are:

$$F_g^i = -\frac{m c^2}{2} \left(0, \frac{da_1}{dx}, \frac{da_2}{dy}, \frac{da_3}{dz} \right). \quad (26)$$

2.6 Massive particle energy

The general metric is given by eq. (19). For a massive particle at rest ($dx^1 = dx^2 = dx^3 = 0$), the proper time is:

$$d\tau = dt' = \sqrt{a_0 a_1 a_2 a_3} dt.$$

The frequency relationship between the bases \mathbf{e}_i and \mathbf{e}'_i is:

$$\nu = \sqrt{a_0 a_1 a_2 a_3} \nu'.$$

For a massive particle at rest in \mathcal{C}' that decays into a photon, the energy in \mathbf{e}'_i is $E' = h \nu' =$

$m c^2$, where m is the particle's rest mass and h is Planck's constant. In the basis \mathbf{e}_i , the photon's frequency is $\nu = \sqrt{a_0 a_1 a_2 a_3} \nu'$, and its energy is $E = h \nu$. Thus:

$$E = \sqrt{a_0 a_1 a_2 a_3} m c^2. \quad (27)$$

In the reference frame \mathcal{C}' , the particle has a momentum $\mathbf{p}' = (p'^j)$, for $j = 1, 2, 3$ with components in the basis \mathbf{e}'_j given by $p'^j = m \frac{dx'^j}{d\tau}$. Given that $dx'^j = \frac{1}{\sqrt{a_0 a_j}} dx^j$, the relationship between the momentum components in the bases \mathbf{e}'_j and \mathbf{e}_j is expressed as $p'^j = m \frac{1}{\sqrt{a_0 a_j}} \frac{dx^j}{d\tau} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{a_0 a_j}} p^j$, for $j = 1, 2, 3$, where $p^j = m \frac{dx^j}{d\tau}$ are the momentum components in the basis \mathbf{e}_j . Thus, the energy in the basis \mathbf{e}_i is given by:

$$\begin{aligned}E^2 &= a_0 a_1 a_2 a_3 E'^2 \\ &= a_0 a_1 a_2 a_3 (m^2 c^4 + \mathbf{p}' \cdot \mathbf{p}' c^2) \\ &= a_0 a_1 a_2 a_3 \left(m^2 c^4 + \sum_{j=1}^3 \frac{(p^j c)^2}{a_0 a_j} \right).\end{aligned}\quad (28)$$

3 Distances measurement

3.1 Methodology and notation

The length of an object can be measured in three different ways:

Standard meter: The length is measured using a physical standard. This physical distance is denoted by D .

Light travel time: The length D is determined by

measuring the time taken for light to cover the distance. This time interval is converted to a spatial distance by multiplying by the speed of light $c = 299,792,458, m/s$. This distance by D_t .

Number of wavelengths: The length D is measured by counting the number of wavelengths of a specific light source required to cover the distance. This count is multiplied by the wavelength to obtain the distance, denoted by D_λ .

We perform the three measurements in the initial reference frame \mathcal{C} , where the meter is defined such that the three results are identical: $D = D_t = D_\lambda$. Subsequently, we transfer the material object and the measuring instruments to another reference frame \mathcal{C}' . We repeat the same measurements, denoted as D' , D'_t and D'_λ . Finally, we compare the primed and unprimed results.

3.2 Distance measurement in general relativity

We assume that the relative velocity between the two reference frames \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{C}' is zero. The speed of electromagnetic radiation emitted from \mathcal{C}' is c in the basis \mathbf{e}'_i and ac in the basis \mathbf{e}_i .

Standard meter. The ratio of the object's length to the standard meter is independent of the reference frame, as both physical distances are affected identically when changing the reference frame: $D' = D$.

Light travel time. Electromagnetic radiation emitted in \mathcal{C} requires a time $t_1 = D/c$ to cover D in the basis \mathbf{e}_i . In the same basis \mathbf{e}_i , the speed of radiation emitted in \mathcal{C}' is ac , so the travel time to cover D is $t_2 = D/(ac)$. In the base \mathbf{e}'_i , the travel time is $t'_2 = \sqrt{a} t_2 = D/(\sqrt{a}c)$. The relationship between the travel times t' in \mathcal{C}' and t in \mathcal{C} is:

$$t' = t/\sqrt{a}. \quad (29)$$

The corresponding distance in \mathcal{C}' based on light travel time is:

$$D'_t = D/\sqrt{a}. \quad (30)$$

The light travel time depends on the reference frame and increases as the relative speed of light decreases.

Number of wavelengths. The number of wavelengths to cover the length of the object is denoted by N in \mathcal{C} and N' in \mathcal{C}' . Following a similar derivation, we find:

$$N' = N/\sqrt{a} \quad (31)$$

$$D'_\lambda = D/\sqrt{a} \quad (32)$$

The number of wavelengths increases as the relative speed of light decreases.

In the framework of general relativity:

- The only method to define a length independently of the reference frame is by using a standard meter.

- Time and wavelengths distances scale proportionally to $1/\sqrt{a}$.
- The interaction range for the weak, strong and electromagnetic forces is directly related to the relative speed of light and can be expressed by $D'_\lambda = D/\sqrt{a}$.
- The differences between these three measurement methods depends on the gravitational field, its direction eqs. (43), (44) and on the temporal evolution eq. (57). At scales easily accessible to current observations, these differences remain minimal and challenging to measure. However, they become significant near a black hole or in the context of early universe.

Numerical example

A standard meter is defined at the Earth's surface in a horizontal position according to the methodology established by the BIPM. We measure D_λ , in the horizontal direction denoted by $D_{\lambda\parallel}$ and in the vertical direction denoted by $D_{\lambda\perp}$. According to eqs. (31), (43) and (44), the relationship is given by:

$$D_{\lambda\perp} = D_{\lambda\parallel} \sqrt{\frac{c_{\parallel}}{c_{\perp}}} \approx 1 + \frac{GM}{2rc^2}. \quad (33)$$

The mass of the Earth is $M = 5.97 \times 10^{24}$ kg and its radius is $r = 6360$ km. Consequently, $D_{\lambda\perp}$ is ≈ 0.35 nm longer than $D_{\lambda\parallel}$.

3.3 Distance measurement in special relativity

The same analysis could be applied to special relativity, but it is beyond the scope of this study.

4 Schwarzschild metric

We consider a spherically symmetric system with a central mass M . Three reference frames, denoted \mathcal{C} , \mathcal{C}' and \mathcal{C}'' , are defined, each associated with a coordinates basis $\mathbf{e}_i, \mathbf{e}'_i, \mathbf{e}''_i$, respectively, where the subscript c or s indicates Cartesian or spherical coordinates. A massive particle with mass m is in free fall. The reference frame \mathcal{C}'' is the proper inertial frame of the particle. The reference frame \mathcal{C}' is stationary relative to M and \mathcal{C} with its position redefined at each instant to coincide with the particle. The reference frame \mathcal{C} is located at infinity, where the gravitational effects of M are negligible. The particle's velocity is denoted by v' in \mathcal{C}' .

4.1 Derivation

We define the coordinate transformation from the proper inertial reference frame \mathcal{C}'' to the reference frame \mathcal{C} .

Definition of the transformation

In the Cartesian basis \mathbf{e}''_{ci} , the displacement four-vector is given by:

$$ds = ds_{\mathbf{e}''_c} = \begin{pmatrix} c dt'' \\ dx'' \\ dy'' \\ dz'' \end{pmatrix}. \quad (34)$$

Since \mathcal{C}'' is an inertial reference frame, its Minkowski metric is:

$$\begin{aligned} ds^2 &= ds_{\mathbf{e}''_c}^T \eta ds_{\mathbf{e}''_c} \\ &= -c^2 dt''^2 + dx''^2 + dy''^2 + dz''^2. \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

We obtain the displacement four-vector ds in the Cartesian basis \mathbf{e}'_c by applying the Lorentz transformation Λ . The relationship is given by:

$$ds_{\mathbf{e}''_c} = \Lambda ds_{\mathbf{e}'_c}.$$

Since the Minkowski metric is invariant under the Lorentz transformation, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} ds^2 &= ds_{\mathbf{e}''_c}^T \eta ds_{\mathbf{e}''_c} \\ &= -c^2 dt''^2 + dx''^2 + dy''^2 + dz''^2. \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

The displacement can be transformed from Cartesian to spherical coordinates using the Jacobian matrix J , such that:

$$ds_{\mathbf{e}'_c} = J ds_{\mathbf{e}'_s} \quad \text{and thus:} \quad ds_{\mathbf{e}''_c} = \Lambda J ds_{\mathbf{e}'_s}.$$

This yields:

$$ds^2 = -c^2 dt''^2 + dr''^2 + r^2 d\theta''^2 + r^2 \sin^2 \theta' d\phi''^2.$$

We define the matrix S_r . The energy of the system is invariant over time, so $a_0 = 1$. Given the spherical symmetry of the system, the speed of light varies only in the radial direction, implying $a_2 = a_3 = 1$, and depends solely on the radius r . We denote $a = a_1(r)$ and the matrix S_r is given by:

$$S_r = \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{a} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1/\sqrt{a} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{with} \quad ds_{\mathbf{e}'_s} = S_r ds_{\mathbf{e}_s}.$$

We obtain the following transformation for the displacement four-vector:

$$ds_{\mathbf{e}''_c} = \Lambda J S_r ds_{\mathbf{e}_s}. \quad (37)$$

Thus, the metric is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} ds^2 &= ds_{\mathbf{e}''_c}^T \eta ds_{\mathbf{e}''_c} \\ &= (\Lambda J S_r ds_{\mathbf{e}_s})^T \eta \Lambda J S_r ds_{\mathbf{e}_s} \\ &= -a c^2 dt^2 + \frac{1}{a} dr^2 + r^2 d\theta^2 + r^2 \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2. \end{aligned} \quad (38)$$

a calculation.

The gravitational force \mathbf{F}_g acting on the particle can be calculated, as described in Section 2.5, using the metric in eq. (38).

The only non-zero component is the radial component, which corresponds to the Newton's gravitational force:

$$F_g^r = -\frac{mc^2}{2} \frac{da}{dr} = -\frac{GmM}{r^2}. \quad (39)$$

Note: The same result can be obtained using the conservation of energy:

$$dE + F_g^r dr' = 0 \quad \text{with} \quad E = \sqrt{a} m c^2.$$

This yields:

$$F_g^r = -\frac{dE}{dr'} = -\sqrt{a} \frac{dE}{dr} = -\frac{mc^2}{2} \frac{da}{dr}.$$

From this, we deduce:

$$\frac{da}{dr} = \frac{2GM}{r^2 c^2}. \quad (40)$$

Integration with respect to r , with the boundary condition $a(\infty) = 1$, gives:

$$a = 1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}. \quad (41)$$

Using eqs. (41) and (38), we obtain the Schwarzschild metric:

$$\begin{aligned} ds^2 = & - \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}\right) c^2 dt^2 \\ & + \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}\right)^{-1} dr^2 \\ & + r^2 d\theta^2 + r^2 \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2. \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

Radial and tangential relative speeds of light

The coefficient a determines the radial speed of light c_\perp , as a function of the distance from the center of mass in the basis \mathbf{e}_s , with the conditions $ds^2 = 0$, $d\theta = 0$ and $d\phi = 0$:

$$c_\perp/c = a = 1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}. \quad (43)$$

The tangential speed of light c_\parallel in the basis \mathbf{e}_s differs because the spatial dimensions in the tangential directions are not modified, with the condition $ds^2 = 0$ and $dr = 0$:

$$c_\parallel/c = \sqrt{a} = \sqrt{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}}. \quad (44)$$

It is impossible to cross the Schwarzschild radius $\frac{2GM}{c^2}$, as all speeds become zero at the Schwarzschild radius.

4.2 Energy calculation

The energy of a mass m in \mathbf{e}_s can be calculated using the formula in eq. (28) with $a_0 = a_2 = a_3 =$

1 and $a_1 = 1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}$. We set the coordinate differentials as $dx_1 = dr$, $dx_2 = 0$, $dx_3 = r d\phi$. The proper time derivative is denoted as $\dot{x} = \frac{dx}{d\tau}$. Thus, in the basis \mathbf{e}_s , the energy is given by:

$$E^2 = \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}\right)(m^2 c^4 + m^2 c^2 \frac{\dot{r}^2}{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}} + m^2 c^2 r^2 \dot{\phi}^2) \quad (45)$$

During free fall, the total energy remains constant: the rest mass energy mc^2 is progressively converted into kinetic energy. This formula demonstrates the equivalence between the inertial mass and the gravitational mass.

The energy E_g released when the radial distance changes from infinity to a radius R , where R is greater than the Schwarzschild radius $R_s = 2GM/c^2$, can be calculated for a particle with zero velocity ($\dot{r} = 0$ and $\dot{\phi} = 0$). Using the substitution $dr' = \frac{dr}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{R_s}{r}}}$, the energy is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} E_g &= \int_{\infty}^R F_g^r dr' \\ &= \int_{\infty}^R -\frac{GmM}{r^2} \frac{dr}{\sqrt{1 - R_s/r}} \\ &= \left[-m c^2 \sqrt{1 - R_s/r}\right]_{\infty}^R \\ &= m c^2 (1 - \sqrt{1 - R_s/R}) \\ &= m c^2 - E. \end{aligned} \quad (46)$$

The total energy is conserved: $E + E_g = m c^2$.

At the Schwarzschild radius, as observed from the

reference frame \mathcal{C} , the particle's energy E is zero and the released energy is $E_g = m c^2$.

4.3 Slight deflection of light

The deflection angle α of a light ray, when its radial speed varies according to eq. (43) can be calculated using Einstein's formula [2]:

$$\alpha = \frac{4GM}{Rc^2}.$$

This result is consistent with that obtained from the Schwarzschild metric [5].

4.4 Trajectories of a massive particle

We consider motion in the equatorial plane. Due to the spherical symmetry of the system, the force is purely radial, and the angular momentum h of the particle is conserved, given by $h = r^2 \dot{\phi}$. The total energy E of the system is also conserved. We define the dimensionless energy parameter $k = E/(mc^2)$. Using the eq. (45), and substituting $E = k m c^2$ and $\dot{\phi} = \frac{h}{r^2}$, we obtain:

$$k^2 c^2 = \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r}\right) \left(c^2 + \frac{\dot{r}^2}{1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r}} + h^2/r^2\right)$$

\Leftrightarrow

$$c^2(k^2 - 1) = \dot{r}^2 + \frac{h^2}{r^2} \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r}\right) - \frac{2GM}{r}.$$

This is the equation of motion for a particle in the Schwarzschild geometry [5].

5 Cosmology

Homogeneous universe

Friedmann-Lemaître equations, which govern cosmic expansion, are derived from a simplified model of the universe based on the following assumption: on a large scales (of order of a few billion of light-years), the universe is homogeneous and isotropic. Consequently, its expansion can be modelled using only two parameters: the average energy density and pressure. This results in a single stress-energy tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$ in Einstein's equation (1) that applies to the entire universe across all points and scales. Based on our interpretation, gravity arises not from spacetime curvature, but from the relative change in the speed of light. For a gravitational effect to occur, the mass density must be heterogeneous.

Let us define the S matrix for a homogeneous and isotropic universe. In such a universe, no gravitational effects arise, so $S_1 = S_2 = S_3 = \mathbb{1}$. According to eq. (27), $S_0 = \mathbb{1}$ is required to maintain constant energy. Consequently, the solution to Einstein's eq. (1) is $S = \mathbb{1}$ corresponding to Minkowski metric. The stress-energy tensor and the cosmological constant are both zero.

From a gravitational perspective, a homogeneous and isotropic universe is an empty, flat and static space.

Heterogeneous universe

Although the universe appears homogeneous on

a large scales, it is inherently heterogeneous due to the nature of matter. The average matter density in the universe is estimated to approximately 0.25 protons per cubic meter. If this matter were uniformly distributed in the early universe, it would have been homogeneous on scales of few hundred meters (considering the material distances). However, gravitational interactions have since reorganized matter into structures such as stars and galaxies. Currently, the heterogeneity has increased by a factor of approximately 10^{22} . This process has released a tremendous amount of energy, which is likely the origin of the observed expansion of the universe.

Universe apparent expansion

In our model, the universe is static. The apparent expansion of the universe observed from Earth is attributed solely to an increase in the speed of light, caused by an increase in energy ($E = \sqrt{a}mc^2$). Baryogenesis itself would have required a significantly higher speed of light than its current value. An infinite speed of light (implying zero interaction distances) would be necessary to achieve a completely homogeneous and isotropic universe.

Consequently, the speed of light is not a monotonic function of time, and cosmological processes likely extended over a period far longer than the 13.8 billion years estimated based on a constant Hubble parameter.

5.1 Local metric of universe expansion

While a global metric for the universe cannot be defined, a local metric can be established. Consider two reference frames: \mathcal{C}' , located in the future or past, and \mathcal{C} , located in the present at $t = 0$, each with basis vectors \mathbf{e}'_i and \mathbf{e}_i , respectively. The coordinates of a displacement four-vector \mathbf{ds} in \mathcal{C}' expressed in the bases \mathbf{e}'_i and \mathbf{e}_i are (dt', dx', dy', dz') and (dt, dx, dy, dz) , respectively. As the apparent spatial intervals are larger in the future reference frame \mathcal{C}' , the time interval is smaller. This relationship can be described by a transformation S_0 , where $a(t)$ is an increasing function of time with $a(0) = 1$:

$$ds'_e = S_0 ds_e = \begin{pmatrix} dt' \\ dx' \\ dy' \\ dz' \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} dt/\sqrt{a(t)} \\ \sqrt{a(t)}dx \\ \sqrt{a(t)}dy \\ \sqrt{a(t)}dz \end{pmatrix}. \quad (47)$$

The speed of light in the reference frame \mathcal{C}' at time t , as observed from \mathcal{C} , is given by $c(t) = \frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{dx'}{dt'}/a(t)$:

$$c(t) = c/a(t). \quad (48)$$

The metric in the reference frame \mathcal{C}' is:

$$ds^2 = -c^2 dt'^2 + dx'^2 + dy'^2 + dz'^2.$$

By applying the transformation (47), we obtain:

$$ds^2 = -\frac{c^2}{a(t)} dt^2 + a(t) (dx^2 + dy^2 + dz^2). \quad (49)$$

All electromagnetic radiation observed from Earth appears redshifted, as our clock ticks faster relative to distant sources.

It can be noted that the metric in eq. (53) is inconsistent: the frequency of light emitted from a point and reflected back to its origin should remain unchanged (since the proper time is invariant). This implies that the frequency decreases during the outward journey and increases during the return journey, suggesting that the frequency of light from a distant star (corresponding to the return journey) should increase.

5.2 Cosmic microwave background (CMB)

The relationship between the observed frequency ν of electromagnetic radiation and its emitted frequency ν' is:

$$\nu = \sqrt{a(t)} \nu' \quad \text{with } t < 0 \quad \text{and} \quad a(t) < 1. \quad (50)$$

It is estimated that the cosmic microwave background (CMB) was emitted when the universe had a temperature of $T' = 3000 \text{ K}$. Its current effective black body temperature is approximately

$T = 3 K$. According to Planck's law, the spectral radiance of a black body at frequency ν' and temperature T' is given by:

$$B_\nu(\nu', T') = \frac{2 h \nu'^3}{c^2} \frac{1}{e^{\frac{h\nu'}{kT'}} - 1} \quad (51)$$

$$\implies B_\nu(\nu, T) = \frac{2 h \nu^3}{a(t)^{3/2} c^2} \frac{1}{e^{k\frac{h\nu}{\sqrt{a(t)}T'}} - 1}.$$

where k is the Boltzmann constant and h is the Planck constant.

Consequently, the relationship between T and T' is:

$$T = T' \sqrt{a(t)}. \quad (52)$$

The relative speed of light has been increased by a factor of $(T'/T)^2 \approx 10^6$ since the emission of the CMB.

5.3 Relationship between a and the Hubble parameter

The scale factor ($R(t)$) appears in the flat Friedmann-Lemaître-Robertson-Walker (FLRW) metric, given by:

$$ds^2 = -c^2 dt^2 + R^2(t) (dx^2 + dy^2 + dz^2) \quad (53)$$

The Hubble parameter H_0 is defined as [5]:

$$H_0 = \frac{\dot{R}(t_0)}{R(t_0)} = \frac{\dot{R}_0}{R_0}. \quad (54)$$

Electromagnetic radiation is emitted by a nearby star (reference frame \mathcal{C}') at the time t' and

observed at the present time t_0 ($t' < t_0$), where the time difference satisfies $t_0 - t' \ll t_0$. The scale factor $R(t)$ can be approximated using a first-order Taylor expansion around t_0 : $R(t') \approx R_0 (1 + (t' - t_0) H_0)$. The relationship between the emitted frequency ν' and the observed ν as described in [5], is given by:

$$\frac{\nu'}{\nu} = \frac{R(t_0)}{R(t')} \approx \frac{1}{1 + H_0(t' - t_0)}. \quad (55)$$

Using eqs. (50) and (55), we obtain:

$$\frac{R_0}{R(t')} = \frac{\sqrt{a(t_0)}}{\sqrt{a(t')}}. \quad (56)$$

$a(t)$ can be approximated using a first-order Taylor expansion around t_0 : $a(t') \approx a_0 (1 + \dot{a}_0/a_0(t' - t_0))$. We obtain:

$$a(t') = a_0 (1 + 2H_0(t' - t_0)). \quad (57)$$

As the Hubble parameter $H_0 \approx 70 \text{ km/s/Mpc} \approx 2.27 \times 10^{-18} \text{ s}^{-1}$, the relative speed of light increases by approximately 4m/s per 100 years.

5.4 Measurement of the relative variation of light with respect to time

The speed of light is invariant in all proper reference frame; its relative variation cannot be measured directly and must be assessed indirectly

through related physical quantities:

Frequency shift. When electromagnetic radiation is emitted and reflected back to its point of origin, its frequency undergoes a redshift, decreasing by approximately $H_0 = 2.27 \times 10^{-18} \text{ s}^{-1}$, equivalent to a relative variation of $-7.16 \times 10^{-11} \text{ yr}^{-1}$, as measured at the emission location.

Variation in the number of wavelengths. The number of wavelengths N , required to cover a material distance D is measured at times t_0 and t . According to (31), the number of wavelengths evolves as:

$$N(t) = \sqrt{\frac{a(t)}{a(t_0)}} N(t_0) \quad (58)$$

$$\approx (1 - (t - t_0) H_0) N(t_0).$$

The relative variation in the number of wavelengths to cover a fixed material distance is approximately $-7.16 \times 10^{-11} \text{ yr}^{-1}$.

Variation in travel time. The travel time Δt required for light to cover a fixed material distance is measured at times t_0 and t . According to eq. (29), the travel time evolves as:

$$\Delta t(t) \approx \Delta t(t_0) (1 - (t - t_0) H_0). \quad (59)$$

The relative variation in the travel time to cover a fixed material distance, is approximately $-7.16 \times 10^{-11} \text{ yr}^{-1}$.

6 Conclusion

We propose a consistent alternative interpretation of general relativity that unifies special and general relativity based on the common principle of energy conservation.

The appropriate interpretation (spacetime curvature or variable speed of light) can be determined by measuring the light travel time along the length of a material object. If the light travel time remains constant, the spacetime is curved. Conversely, if the light travel time varies with respect to time or the direction of the gravitational field, then the speed of light is variable.

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